

Common Infrastructure for National Cohorts in Europe, Canada, and Africa - CINECA -

Deliverable D2.1

CanDIG and ELIXIR AAI interoperability demonstration

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Lead Beneficiary:	European Molecular Biology Laboratory
WP Leader(s):	Michal Procházka (MU), Mikael Linden (CSC)
Contributing Partner(s):	MU, CSC, SickKids, ClinicaGeno, EMBL-EBI, UCT
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Authors of this Deliverable:	Michal Prochazka (MU), Mikael Linden (CSC), Amanjeev Sethi (SickKids), Thomas Binsl (CGO), Alex Michie (CGO), Mamana Mbiyavanga (UCT), Dylan Spalding (EMBL-EBI)
Reviewed by:	Tommi Nyrönen (CSC), Jonathan Dursi (SickKids)
Approved by:	Thomas Keane (EMBL-EBI)
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1. Executive Summary

This deliverable demonstrates authentication and authorisation interoperability between the ELIXIR and CanDIG infrastructures. Users from one infrastructure can access services from the other. The interoperability covers user identification and authentication as well as the transfer of the authorisation claims following the GA4GH Passport and AAI OpenID Connect protocol (OIDC) profile specifications.

2. Project objectives

With this deliverable, the project has contributed to the following objectives:

- a) To ensure Authentication and Authorisation Infrastructure (AAI) is interoperable between European, Canadian, and African cohorts.
- b) To upgrade ELIXIR and Canada AAI to support GA4GH protocols to ensure CINECA interoperability with other global cohort infrastructures.

3. Detailed report on the deliverable

3.1 Background

Allowing cross infrastructure authentication and enabling delivery of the authorisation information between ELIXIR and CanDIG allows users to access services regardless of their technical connection to one of the infrastructures. Research can be done on the data deposited in both infrastructures and data providers will be able to uniquely identify users from both infrastructures.

This section introduces the relevant data access models and phases and highlights the ELIXIR and CanDIG AAI systems, including their use of GA4GH Passports¹. Finally it introduces the user scenarios covered in this deliverable.

Tiered access to data

Global Alliance for Genomics and Health (GA4GH) is promoting a three-tier access model for sensitive data:

- **Public access tier** consists of public data. No user authentication and specific authorisation is needed.
- **Registered access tier** consists of data which is sensitive but available for all qualified researchers without further approvals. The researcher needs to demonstrate they are a researcher in a good standing and they need to make the attestations for registered access, for instance that they will not try to re-identify individuals from the data they access. In GA4GH Passport specification, registered access tier is catered by AcceptedTermsAndPolicies and ResearcherStatus Visas [1].
- **Controlled access tier** is the classic data access model for sensitive data. A researcher needs to prepare a data access request, attach a research plan to it and submit the request to a

¹ For a wider introduction to GA4GH Passports, see a related [GA4GH webinar](#).

competent data access committee (DAC) for approval. Data access is permitted only on DAC approval for researchers who have signed a data access agreement. In GA4GH Passport specification, controlled access tier is catered by the ControlledAccessGrants Visa.

Full access to genotype and phenotype data belongs normally to controlled access tier because they enable identifying the sample donor. Registered access is aimed at accessing summary and aggregated data, such as the number of samples in the cohort that have a certain genomic variant. Registered access serves in particular the purposes of data discovery and can be carried out, for instance, using the GA4GH Beacon API.

Data access phases

Access to data can be split to the three chronological phases of authentication, authorisation and access control enforcement.

- **User authentication** ensures the identity of the users and can be done on-line using for instance, passwords or multi-factor authentication. This phase covers also the initial proof of identity that the user has to do to register and receive their authentication credentials.
- **Authorisation** is the phase where the user receives the permission to access a service in a registered or controlled access tier. For registered access, the user needs to demonstrate they are a researcher in a good standing and make the attestations for registered access. For controlled access, a competent DAC needs to approve a researcher's data access request and sign a data access agreement with them. As a result, the user receives a GA4GH Visa that they can use to demonstrate their data access permissions.
- **Access control enforcement** is the phase where the user presents their GA4GH passport (that is a collection of their GA4GH Visas) to the environment where the data access is done and the environment validates them to enforce access. For registered access, access control is enforced for instance by a GA4GH Beacon implementation that checks the user has proper Visas for registered access. For controlled access, access control can be enforced for instance by the GA4GH htsgat API implementation that checks the user has proper ControlledAccessGrants Visas for streaming a particular data object.

GA4GH Passports can enable federated analysis in a distributed environment where the three steps can be carried out by different organisations in different geographical locations. For instance, user authentication is done at their home university, authorisation is received from a competent DAC and access control enforcement takes place in a cloud where the datasets are made available for analysis. Later in this deliverable, we will use a table to indicate which phases take place in CanDIG and which in ELIXIR.

ELIXIR AAI

The ELIXIR AAI [2] provides services for data providers and authorities for researcher identification, authentication and authorisation. The ELIXIR AAI assigns each end user a permanent unique identifier (ELIXIR ID), which allows them to use the same credentials (e.g. home university username and password) to login to services that belong to ELIXIR. The data access and resource allocations are stored as part of the identity. The ELIXIR AAI allows authentication against services associated with ELIXIR research infrastructure, and in the long term, it can be used with other research

infrastructures and e-infrastructures. There is also an ongoing activity to migrate the ELIXIR AAI into the LifeScience AAI [3] which will provide similar service across the wider life sciences research community in Europe.

The authentication of the identity is done by external authentication providers, such as eduGAIN, Google, LinkedIn and ORCID. The ELIXIR service providers hosting sensitive data require an added level of assurance regarding user authentication, therefore ELIXIR AAI provides various levels of user verification. For the most sensitive data and computing services, two-factor authentication is also available.

User authorisation to access services can be based on many factors. For some services, authorisation is based on the user's current affiliation. This user information can be received from the Identity Provider of the user's Home Organisation. For some services, the user's authorisation and profile are based on their group memberships managed by the Perun² software integrated to the ELIXIR AAI. ELIXIR uses the GA4GH concept of "a bona fide researcher", where the researcher may use various mechanisms to demonstrate their researcher status, such as their home organisation or other users vouching that they are a member of the scientific community in good standing, and therefore eligible to access the services.

The most sensitive services, such as access to sensitive human datasets, requires presenting a research plan to a Data Access Committee (DAC). ELIXIR AAI is able to query users' data access permissions from the European Genome-phenome Archive (EGA) and assemble them to their GA4GH Passports for delivery to downstream Passport consumers. The REMS³ software (Resource Entitlement Management System) supporting the data access request process is also integrated to ELIXIR AAI in conjunction with the GA4GH Passport standard.

CanDIG AAI

Fundamental to CanDIG⁴, as a platform, is the national scale of analysis but using locally-controlled data. The CanDIG platform is completely distributed, with no central infrastructure to maintain or secure. Researchers need to be able to readily discover, access, and analyse this information, possibly jointly across sites, while allowing the data stewards to ensure the security and privacy of their data.

CanDIG does this by building on established or in-progress protocols elsewhere such as OpenID Connect for AAI, and using standard FOSS tools like Keycloak as Identity Providers and Brokers. OpenID Connect enables CanDIG to maintain researcher identities locally, i.e. on-site, while allowing for OIDC Claims to be embedded and/or fetched that provide authorisation. These claims allow data stewards to authorise researchers who belong to an institution but need access to a project which may involve more sites than just their own (i.e. prove the "bona fide researcher" status).

User Scenarios

For this deliverable we have identified three use scenarios:

² <https://perun-aai.org>

³ <http://www.elixir-finland.org/en/aai-rems-2/>

⁴ <https://www.distributedgenomics.ca/architecture.html>

1. A CanDIG user wants to access ELIXIR dataset in a computing environment provided by ELIXIR
2. An ELIXIR user wants to access a CanDIG dataset in a computing environment provided by CanDIG
3. An ELIXIR user wants to use their ELIXIR bona fide status to access a registered access Beacon in CanDIG

Notice, that a cross-Atlantic delivery of GA4GH Visas takes place only for the registered access Visas in use scenarios 3 and 4 . Cross-Atlantic delivery of controlled access Visas would be relevant only if also some dataset was replicated overseas, which we are not aware of.

Use scenario 1: A user from CanDIG wants to access sensitive data from a cohort deposited in ELIXIR infrastructure. Access to those data is controlled, therefore proper claims from the CanDIG need to be delivered to ELIXIR.

1. CanDIG user has identified an interesting dataset in EGA
2. CanDIG user applies for access to it and is granted access by a competent DAC
3. CanDIG user accesses the data in a secure computing environment in an ELIXIR node

Distribution of functionality	In CanDIG	In ELIXIR
User authentication	X	
Authorisation (ControlledAccessGrant Visa)		X
Access control enforcement		X

Use scenario 2: A user with ELIXIR identity wants to access sensitive data from a cohort deposited in CanDIG infrastructure. Access to those data is controlled, therefore proper claims from the ELIXIR need to be delivered to CanDIG.

1. ELIXIR user has identified an interesting dataset in the Canadian cohort
2. ELIXIR user applies for access to it and is granted access by a competent DAC
3. ELIXIR user accesses the data in a secure computing environment in Canada (available when the projects that use CanDIG infrastructure launch; using a proof-of-concept instance for this deliverable)

Distribution of functionality	In CanDIG	In ELIXIR
User authentication		X
Authorisation (ControlledAccessGrant Visa)	X	
Access control enforcement	X	

Use Scenario 3: ELIXIR user using CanDIG registered access beacon

1. ELIXIR user wants to access a registered access beacon

2. ELIXIR user demonstrates they are a bona fide researcher and makes the attestations
3. ELIXIR user logs in to the beacon and receives access to registered access tier

Distribution of functionality	In CanDIG	In ELIXIR
User authentication		X
Authorisation (AcceptedTermsAndPolicies and ResearcherStatus Visas)		X
Access control enforcement	X	

Use Scenario 4: CanDIG user using ELIXIR registered access beacon

1. CanDIG user wants to access a registered access beacon
2. CanDIG user demonstrates they are a bona fide researcher and makes the attestations
3. CanDIG user logs in to the beacon and receives access to registered access tier

Distribution of functionality	In CanDIG	In ELIXIR
User authentication	X	
Authorisation (AcceptedTermsAndPolicies and ResearcherStatus Visas)	X	
Access control enforcement		X

3.2 Description of Work

For cross-Atlantic access, both infrastructures must support the same authentication and authorisation protocol. For the ELIXIR/CanDIG interoperability, OpenID Connect protocol (OIDC) is used, as specified in the GA4GH AAI OpenID Connect profile specification. CanDIG is using OIDC natively and ELIXIR AAI has support for OIDC.

Figure 1 depicts how both infrastructures are technically connected. CanDIG institutions (identity providers - IdP) are connected to the ELIXIR OIDC-SAML2 Bridge. Therefore users from CanDIG institutions can access all ELIXIR services permitted for them. CanDIG services are connected to the ELIXIR OIDC Interface as any other ELIXIR services. Because interoperability is not just about authentication both interfaces ELIXIR OIDC-SAML2 Bridge and ELIXIR OIDC Interface are able to release and consume additional claims, e.g. GA4GH Passports and Visas.

Figure 1: ELIXIR AAI and CanDIG technical connection

User flows

Below the user flows and their prerequisites are described.

1. A researcher wants to be able to log into the CanDIG environment using ELIXIR AAI.

Requirements

- The user has registered an ELIXIR ID in ELIXIR.
- At least one CanDIG site is registered as an OpenID Connect Relying Party (RP) of CanDIG Keycloak that relays the user attributes from ELIXIR.

Figure 2: User from ELIXIR wants to access CanDIG RP

2. A researcher wants to be able to log into the ELIXIR environment using CanDIG AAI.

Requirements

- The user has registered an ID in at least one CanDIG home organisation.
- ELIXIR AAI service is added as an OpenID Connect Relying Party with the CanDIG site.

Figure 3: User from CanDIG wants to access ELIXIR RP

Technical solution

On the ELIXIR side we created an ELIXIR OIDC-SAML2 Bridge for CanDIG identity providers. Technically that was realised using SimpleSAMLphp software with modules implemented by ELIXIR, CESNET and Masaryk University. CINECA contributed with modifications and configurations to be interoperable with CanDIG identity and service providers. All codes are available at CESNET's GitHub⁵.

Below is described how the components are connected and their requirements.

1. A researcher wants to be able to log into the CanDIG environment using their ELIXIR ID.
 - a. CanDIG OIDC provider (Keycloak) needs to register in ELIXIR AAI as a Relying Party. This helps with redirecting the ELIXIR user from the CanDIG login resource to ELIXIR.
 - b. Users log in to the CanDIG resources through the ELIXIR OIDC-SAML2 Bridge, where they get an access token. There is no need to modify CanDIG resources.
 - i. ELIXIR OIDC-SAML2 Bridge can filter ELIXIR users based on the access control rights set at ELIXIR side.
 - c. In the access token, ELIXIR AAI releases the `openid`, `profile` and `email` scopes to CanDIG relying parties as well as claims like GA4GH Passports.
 - d. Users have the ability to check/uncheck the claims they want to send to the CanDIG resource.
 - e. The claims from ELIXIR AAI are imported into the CanDIG IdP as user attributes that are then served via the `userinfo` endpoint.

⁵ <https://github.com/CESNET/>

2. A researcher wants to be able to log into the ELIXIR environment using CanDIG AAI.
 - a. ELIXIR AAI has OIDC-SAML2 Bridge.
 - b. ELIXIR AAI registers as an OIDC client in each CanDIG IdP since CanDIG does not have a centralised authentication provider.
 - c. OIDC-SAML2 Bridge provides identity provider discovery service, where the CanDIG user can select Identity provider. (not yet deployed).
 - d. Every user from CanDIG needs to be registered in ELIXIR. He/she will be automatically redirected to the registration page on first access (including accept the acceptable usage policy).
 - e. ELIXIR AAI requires at least `openid`, `profile` and `email` scope.
 - i. In case of fine grained authorisation, ELIXIR AAI is able to consume GA4GH Visas claims.

An example of how the login process works from the user point of view can be seen in Appendix 1. There is a user from ELIXIR who would like to access CanDIG resources. Appendix 2 shows CanDIG user flow when accessing resources in ELIXIR.

3.3 Next steps

Technically the AAI interoperability has now been achieved between ELIXIR and CanDIG. The next steps will be to integrate CanDIG services and identity providers, and to deploy REMS or other systems for managing the DAC.

4. References

[1] Dyke, S., Linden, M., Lappalainen, I., Rambla De Argila, J., Carey, K., Lloyd, D., Spalding, D., Cabili, N., Kerry, G., Foreman, J., Cutts, T., Shabani, M., Rodriguez, L., Haeussler, M., Walsh, B., Jiang, X., Wang, S., Perrett, D., Boughtwood, T., Matern, A., Brookes, A., Cupak, M., Fiume, M., Pandya, R., Tulchinsky, I., Scollen, S., Törnroos, J., Das, S., Evans, A., Malin, B., Beck, S., Brenner, S., Nyrönen, T., Blomberg, N., Firth, H., Hurles, M., Philippakis, A., Rättsch, G., Brudno, M., Boycott, K., Rehm, H., Baudis, M., Sherry, S., Kato, K., Knoppers, B., Baker D., Flicek, P. **Registered access: authorizing data access**. European Journal of Human Genetics volume 26, pages 1721–1731(2018) (<https://doi.org/10.1038/s41431-018-0219-y>)

[2] Linden M, Procházka M, Lappalainen I et al. **Common ELIXIR Service for Researcher Authentication and Authorisation** [version 1; peer review: 3 approved, 1 approved with reservations]. F1000Research 2018, 7(ELIXIR):1199 (<https://doi.org/10.12688/f1000research.15161.1>)

[3] Linden, M., Bucik, D., Gormanns, P., Haley, N., Heikkinen, J., Holub P., Kankaanpää, P., Kouril, D., Kuba, M., Licehammer S., Matyska, L., Nyrönen, T., Prochazka, M., Reihs, R., Romano, P., Sanderson, F., Shigaval A., Smith, C., Tedds J. **Access and User Management System for Life Science -- the Blueprint**. EOSC-Life Deliverable D5.1. (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3386307>)

5. Abbreviations

AAI	Authentication and Authorisation Infrastructure
DAC	Data Access Committee
EGA	European Genome-phenome Archive
FOSS	Free and open-source software
GA4GH	Global Alliance for Genomics and Health
IdP	Identity Provider
OIDC	OpenID Connect
REMS	Resource Entitlement Management System
SAML2	Security Assertion Markup Language version 2

6. Delivery and schedule

Work has been done on time.

7. Adjustments made

OIDC-SAML2 Bridge doesn't provide identity provider discovery service for CanDIG IdPs, because there is just one CanDIG IdP connected now.

8. Appendices

Appendix 1

ELIXIR user's flow when accessing CanDIG Resource

Screencast video demonstrating an ELIXIR user accessing the CanDIG service is available at: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=21i0m0L42MQ>.

Thus user flow matches the use scenarios #2 and #3 presented in section 3.2.

1. When an ELIXIR user accesses CanDIG resource he/she is automatically requested to authenticate. The screenshot shows login page to CanDIG. In our case user selects ELIXIR AAI.

2. The ELIXIR user selects his/her home organisation or social provider.

3. User selected ORCID and authenticates with his/her ORCID ID.

4. When the ELIXIR user comes to CanDIG for the first time ELIXIR presents the attribute consent to him/her.

5. ELIXIR users are authenticated and can now see the CanDIG resources which can properly recognise the user.

Appendix 2

A CanDIG user's flow when accessing an ELIXIR Resource

Screencast video demonstrating a CanDIG user accessing the ELIXIR service is available at: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=UOYQEG0I9Qk>.

Thus user flow matches the use scenarios #1 and #4 presented in section 3.2.

1. A CanDIG user start with the ELIXIR Beacon page

Select your identity provider

your previous selection

or

or

your institutional account

Candig

2. The CanDIG user selects CanDIG to initiate login.

3. The CanDIG authenticates at the CanDIG Identity Provider

eliXIR

Consent about releasing personal information to service beacon-auth-test

<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Identifier of user on a service	85d1b57ec1ab9460915c208faf02790d6cb38d45@elixir-europe.org
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> GA4GH	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• null, signed by ELIXIR• AffiliationAndRole: "affiliate@google.com" asserted 2019-07-23, signed by ELIXIR• AffiliationAndRole: "affiliate@orcid.com" asserted 2020-05-28, signed by ELIXIR• AffiliationAndRole: "member@muni.cz" asserted 2020-05-28, signed by ELIXIR• AffiliationAndRole: "employee@muni.cz" asserted 2020-05-28, signed by ELIXIR• AffiliationAndRole: "affiliate@linkedin.com" asserted 2020-05-15, signed by ELIXIR• AffiliationAndRole: "vyskocilpavel@muni.cz" asserted 2020-05-28, signed by ELIXIR

Do not ask again

4. The CanDIG user confirms the release of their claims from ELIXIR AAI to the ELIXIR Beacon

